

Tollivar:

Using AI to support proactive ethical alignment in organisational decision-making

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Topic overview

This case study explores how the AI governance advisory company Tollivar has created an experimental, AI-assisted ethical assurance protocol designed to help organisations align proposed decisions with globally recognised public-purpose goals such as the UN **Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs)**, **OECD AI Principles**, and other international standards.

Developed by public international law expert Dr Yoriko Otomo, an Expert-in-Residence in The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, the project uses a case study to examine whether the AI-assisted protocol can be used to support real-time governance through assessing e.g. the alignment of major infrastructure or similar development projects with SDGs in BAU decision-making. The intention is to create an open access protocol and, potentially, a commercialised AI agent that can support governments and businesses to make more informed, ethical and traceable decisions.

How do organisations make ethical AI decisions today?

Organisations today operate within an increasingly complex web of standards, regulations and ethical expectations. International frameworks such as the SDGs, OECD AI Principles, UNESCO Ethics Recommendations and human rights conventions set high-level goals relating to AI, but translating these into day-to-day operational decisions is often complex, costly and time-intensive.

Yoriko is an internationally recognised academic working in public international law – particularly in the areas of biodiversity protection, endangered species governance, colonial legal history, and corporate social responsibility. Through this work, she observed two persistent challenges: first, decision-making is often retrogressive and reactive, focused on managing reputational or financial risk after harm occurs, and second, the cost of aligning decisions with global norms is high, requiring interdisciplinary teams of lawyers, environmental specialists, governance experts and consultants.

There is currently no reliable alignment technique that can be adopted proactively by private companies or public organisations.

“We’re facing a rapidly accelerating risk surface globally,” says Yoriko. “The number of businesses adopting AI in their decision-making processes and who operate across jurisdictions is expanding, but risk management is still largely reactive and business-focused rather than aligned with the public interest. We also have to acknowledge that humans aren’t great at dealing with big numbers, multiple variables, technical specificity, or vast amounts of documentation – whereas that’s the sort of scenario in which AI can be really helpful.”

Tollivar’s framework emerged as an attempt to systematise ethical alignment: could AI help organisations run proposed actions through a structured protocol that explicitly references global ethical standards, identifies potential conflicts, and generates a transparent governance record? In that sense, could AI, which is undoubtedly a source of emerging risks, become part of the solution to this cross-border challenge?

Testing AI-assisted alignment

Tollivar has developed an ethical alignment protocol or filter that sits on top of a large language model (LLM), that is being developed as a standalone AI agent. The idea is that any organisation could take a proposed decision – for example, whether to build a logistics corridor through a politically or environmentally sensitive area – and run it through an alignment layer supported by relevant documentation that:

- identifies relevant global and local regulatory norms and standards
- maps stakeholders, with a focus on the most vulnerable groups
- highlights environmental, social and governance factors
- flags potential trade-offs between economic, environmental and human rights considerations
- produces a traceable record of reasoning for review and evaluation.

Importantly, Tollivar does not remove decision-making power from humans: it is designed to support executives and governing boards rather than replacing their judgement.

Yoriko says: “Our idea was to create a reusable pipeline so that any organisation could run its decisions through it and align proposed actions with globally agreed ethical goals. The overall objective is to generate ethical reasoning and impact-aware planning, thereby improving judgement, stakeholder management and governance. We decided to test this add-on layer of contextual documentation with both a locally hosted, custom-built AI ‘personal assistant’ developed by a partner consultancy, and with a widely available large language model, Claude (Opus 4.5).”

A fictitious logistics company (Meridian Transglobal Logistics) was invented to ensure the protocol could be tested safely on synthetic data before working with real corporate information. Both AI environments were populated with the same background documents and were asked the question: “Should the company invest in a new logistics corridor in East Africa when it may run through politically sensitive areas?” Documents included a description of the business and its strategy, a stakeholder map, a risk register, sector-specific ethical guidance, and broader principles developed by organisations such as the UN, OECD and UNESCO.

While the AI agent tended to deliver non-specific responses and often failed to follow instructions (for example, failing to suggest mitigations or to escalate high-risk decisions for human review), Claude performed, in Yoriko’s words, “astonishingly well”. Against the scoring system created to assess both models, the locally hosted agent scored 13/35, while Claude scored 31/35, identifying specific indigenous groups and endangered species, quantifying potential harm, suggesting mitigations, and correctly escalating critical risk.

Yoriko notes, however, that using commercial LLMs for every decision would be financially and environmentally costly and may not be practical for routine use, prompting exploration of alternative deployment approaches that will be discussed later in this case study.

Testing AI-assisted alignment

One of the decision-making protocol’s central innovations is the traceability schema. Each decision produces a documented record – or ‘envelope’ – containing the nature of the proposed action, the stakeholders identified (with particular attention to those with least political power), the global regulations and standards consulted, and any tensions or trade-offs between them. It also records potential harms, including their severity and reversibility, and flags where escalation to board level or specialist review would be appropriate.

The aim is to make the reasoning process transparent and reviewable, which is particularly important in complex cases and where decisions may later come under scrutiny.

Challenges and next steps: Managing conflicting goals and ensuring technical progress

Tollivar sits at the intersection of law, governance, technology and corporate decision-making, and the challenges it faces reflect that complexity. Frameworks such as the SDGs are widely endorsed, but not always consistent within and against one another (for example, economic growth objectives may be in tension with environmental protection ambitions). Selecting which norms to prioritise and how to encode those priorities within an AI-assisted protocol necessarily involves an element of value judgement. As Yoriko notes, part of the value of the protocol lies in deciding how principles should be weighted and presented when they pull in different directions.

Technical constraints have posed another challenge to the protocol's development. Yoriko says: "Having a machine learning engineer on board would have been hugely beneficial. I think I underestimated how important that technical layer would be to the project from the outset, alongside the governance and legal thinking." Yoriko is now seeking funding to help develop the framework, and a key priority will be bringing in engineering expertise to strengthen the model architecture, refine the scoring methodology, and improve the integration of datasets. There has been early interest in Tollivar from government-aligned institutions and regulated industries, which are seen as potential beneficiaries of this type of product.

Future development priorities include expanding the normative library that underpins the protocol (incorporating more detailed and context-specific datasets where possible) and further testing the accuracy and consistency of the impact assessments produced by the system. To help with scalability, Yoriko is looking at alternatives to the potentially expensive and environmentally costly 'LLM documentation add-on' approach. These alternatives include running the protocol locally (a technique known as edge computing) so that fewer calls to a remote LLM are required, or even the development of the protocol as a standalone, commercially available AI agent that can be deployed with a tailored dataset. This would be particularly important if the protocol were to be adopted by public bodies or smaller organisations with limited budgets.

Interoperability and localisation will also be critical for wider adoption. For Tollivar to function across jurisdictions and sectors, it must be adaptable to regionally specific standards and capable of integrating with different regulatory environments. Ensuring that the protocol can be widely accepted is a core part of the design challenge.

Reflections on *The Turing Way* Practitioners Hub

“The Practitioners Hub has been invaluable for me. It gave me technical grounding around data security, IP, and governance, but most of all it provided community and encouragement. The stakeholder mapping sessions and templates were particularly important because they helped me systematise what I’d already been doing intuitively and introduced me to the right vocabulary. That was the moment I realised we could formalise this into a protocol. Without this programme, I honestly don’t think I would have put the project together in this way. The Practitioners Hub also introduced me to a fellow Expert-in-Residence and business, whose support was instrumental in helping me understand the best approach to incorporating AI into our solution.”

Dr Yoriko Otomo,
Founder of Tollivar

Key takeaways

- Proactive ethical alignment may reduce the long-term risks and harms of infrastructure and development projects more effectively than reactive or even pre-training approaches.
- AI excels at synthesising large volumes of documentation and supporting decision-making, but human oversight is critical and cannot be replaced by AI.
- Product testing is necessary throughout the development journey, and in this case, demonstrated the need to find additional ways of building and testing the tool.
- Features such as the Tollivar protocol's 'traceability schema' are essential to ensure transparency and accountability for AI-assisted outputs – particularly in sensitive, high-stakes fields.
- While domain-specific knowledge is crucial, working alongside technical experts, as well as relevant government agencies, is also important for getting an AI-based product off the ground and developing it to its full potential.

Contributors and acknowledgements

This case study is published under *The Turing Way Practitioners Hub* 2025-26 Cohort – case study series. The Practitioners Hub is *The Turing Way* project that works with experts from partnering organisations to promote data science best practices. In 2025, The Turing Way team welcomed **Yoriko Otomo and Ben Otomo from Tollivar** as Experts-in-Residence to discuss and share their implementation approaches to data science and AI, as well as build additional skills around best practices in responsible, ethical, and collaborative working. We thank them for leading the development of this case study. Cassio Zatará contributed his technical expertise in conversations along the way.

The Turing Way Practitioner's Hub was supported by Innovate UK BridgeAI from 2023–2026. BridgeAI empowers UK businesses in high-growth sectors, driving productivity and economic growth through the adoption of Artificial Intelligence. The programme bridges the gap between developers and end-users, fostering user-driven AI technologies.

With a focus on ethics, transparency, and data privacy, BridgeAI aims to build trust and confidence in the development of AI solutions. Strengthening AI leadership, supporting workforces, and promoting responsible innovation, BridgeAI shapes a collaborative and AI-enabled future.

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The Turing Way Practitioners Hub's 2025-26 Cohort was co-delivered by **Arielle Bennett**, Senior Researcher – Open Source Practices and Dr Ann Borda, Senior Research Community Manager. **Stuart Gillespie** is the technical writer for this case study, and others in the series. **Léllé Demertzi** is the Research Project Manager and the Case Study Liaison for this case study.

The Turing Way Practitioners Hub, designed and launched in 2023 by Dr Malvika Sharan, aims to accelerate the adoption of best practices. Through a six-month cohort-based program, the Hub facilitates knowledge sharing, skill exchange, case study co-creation, and the adoption of open science practices. It also fosters a network of 'Experts in Residence' across partnering organisations.

For any comments, questions or collaboration with *The Turing Way*, please email: theturingway@gmail.com

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